

THE IMPORTANCE OF PRODUCTIVE SKILLS IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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Annotation: This article discusses the notion and value of productive skills in language learning. Productive skills, known as active skills, are essential for effective communication. With the help of learning productive skills, students have a chance of practicing real life activities in classroom. By teaching productive skills, teachers help students not only develop their linguistic competence but also express themselves in various contexts, such as social, academic and professional. This article aims to pay much attention to the peculiarities of productive skills and their importance in teaching English.

Key words: Productive skills, speaking skill, conversation, writing skill, communication, brainstorming.

Productive skills are known as active skills. Learners use these skills to produce language. Productive skills are crucial as they give students the opportunity to practice real life activities in classroom. Learners receive language by listening and try to produce language through productive skills. Speaking is the delivery of language through mouth. To speak, we create sounds using many parts of our body. According to Chastain [1], speaking is a productive skill that involves many components, such as grammar, strategy, sociolinguistics and discourse; for him speaking is more than simply making the right sounds, choosing the right words or getting the constructions correct [2]. Speaking is probably the language skill that most language learners wish to perfect as soon as possible. Speaking is more frequently used than writing. The main function of spoken language is to socialize individuals. On the contrary to writing, spoken language is produced and processed in real time, the speaker and hearer have limited time to plan and produce what they want to say and understand what they hear. Speech is generally used in face-to-face conversations; it is temporary, spontaneous and variable. Spoken language is supported by body language such as gestures or facial expressions (often called non-verbal communication).

Speaking is a productive skill. It involves putting a message together, communicating the message and interacting with other people. McDonough and Shaw [5] pointed that, for genuine communication speaking is desired. It involves expressing ideas and opinions, expressing a wish or a desire to do something; negotiating and/or solving a particular problem. So speaking is the oral production of a language on the other hand writing is the written form of a language.

According to McDonough and Shaw [5], speaking is a process difficult in many ways to dissociate from listening. Speaking is to interact with others in society. If we make contrast speaking with writing then speaking can be produced and processed in real time, the speaker and listener have limited time to plan and produce what they want to say and understand what they listen. Spoken is occurred in face-to-face conversations. It is also done by body language for instance gestures, facial expressions. Although not a set curriculum is there in most educational institutions, speaking skills have been found to be a fundamental skill necessary for a learner's success in life. Learners often evaluate their success in language learning on the basis of how well they feel they have improved in their spoken language proficiency. Matin claims [6] someone's fluency in speaking measures his/ her proficiency in that language.

Students having ability to translate their thoughts and ideas into words are found to be more successful in school. Without developing good speaking skills, students has to suffer lifelong consequences because of their inability. Ability of speaking English also plays an important role in developing reading and writing skills. As Rivers says, when we read and write, we use what we know of the language orally. Speaking skill is required everywhere, from simple conversation to formal public speaking. As Wilson [7] argues, talking can be used to connect with others, explore and understand the world and reveal oneself.

Writing is the productive skill in written mode. It, too, is more complicated than it seems at first, and often seems to be the hardest of the skills, even for native speakers of a language, since it involves not just a graphic representation of speech, but the development and presentation of thoughts in a structured way.

There are various ways how to define writing. The Blackwell Encyclopaedia of Writings Systems, Florian Coulmas defines a writing system as: "a set of visible or tactile signs used to represent units of language in a systematic way, with the purpose of recording messages which can be retrieved by everyone who knows the language in question and the rules by virtue of which its units are encoded in the writing system." [8] Writing is one way of providing variety in classroom procedures. It

provides a learner with physical evidence of his achievements and he can measure his improvement. It helps to consolidate their grasp of vocabulary and structure, and complements the other language skills. From the four language skills, writing is categorized as one of the productive skills along with speaking since they involve producing language rather than receiving it. These two skills are basically different in various ways. The differences lie on a number of dimensions including textual, features, socio-cultural norm, pattern of use and cognitive process. Writing is slightly different from speaking in term of communication context.

In conclusion, in the presented work we paid much attention to the peculiarities of productive skills. There are two types of productive skills: speaking and writing. Speaking is always intended for face-to-face communication among the audience present, while writing is always used by the writers to express and communicate their ideas to the readers who are actually separated by both time and space distances. Therefore, it requires clearer and more comprehensive message. In other words, when people communicate orally, they can use various types of prosodic features such as pitch, rhythm, pauses that enable them to get feedbacks from the listeners. In contrast, those features of speaking do not exist in writing because the communication context is created by the words alone without having direct interaction between the writer and the reader.

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